

Microwave-Assisted Green Synthesis, Molecular Docking and Biological Assessment of Sulphonyl Pyrimidinone Derivatives as Cholinesterase Inhibitors

Lokkanya Dewangan^{*1,2}, Alok Singh Thakur², Anju Daharia³, Smriti Dewangan¹

¹Shri Rawatpura Sarkar Institute of Pharmacy, Kumhari Durg, Chhattisgarh, India, 490042

²Shri Shankaracharya Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research, Shri Shankaracharya Professional University, Bhilai, Chhattisgarh, India, 490020

³Kamla Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Bhilai, Chhattisgarh, India, 490020

Abstract

This paper involves the development of a potential pharmacophore containing a sulphonyl pyrimidinone lead for treating Alzheimer's disease (AD). The compounds were synthesized by using green synthesis via microwave-assisted methods and characterized through different physicochemical and spectral analyses, and they were evaluated for *in-vitro* Acetylcholinesterase (AChE) and butyrylcholinesterase (BuChE) inhibitory activity using Ellman's assays, with several candidates exhibiting potent inhibition. Notably, compounds **4d** and **4e** demonstrated strong AChE inhibition ($IC_{50} = 31.66 \pm 0.882$ nM and 37.33 ± 1.453 nM, respectively) and BuChE inhibition ($IC_{50} = 33.33 \pm 0.882$ nM and 34.00 ± 1.528 nM, respectively) compared to the Standard drug, i.e., Donepezil (AChE $IC_{50} = 51.66$ nM, BuChE $IC_{50} = 59.00$ nM). The most promising compounds were further evaluated for *in vivo* cognitive enhancement by the Y-maze spontaneous alternation test in mice. There was significant improvement in spatial working memory of treated groups over the controls ($p < 0.05$), which confirms the neuroprotective property of these molecules. In order to get a molecular understanding of activity, molecular docking analysis was done on the crystal structures of human AChE (PDB ID 4ey7) and BChE (PDB ID: 4TPK). Significant interactions with the catalytic active site and peripheral anionic site residues were identified, which is consistent with the observed *in vitro* cholinesterase inhibition. Overall, the results suggest that the sulphonyl pyrimidine pharmacophores are promising therapeutic candidates for further development as a multifunctional agent for the treatment of Alzheimer's disease.

Keywords: Alzheimer's disease, cholinesterase inhibition, Molecular Docking, sulphonyl pyrimidinone derivatives, neuroprotection, Y-maze test

Introduction

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a neurodegenerative condition that is progressive and mainly occurs with aging, resulting in cognitive decline, memory loss, functional disability, and behavioral disturbances. It is a condition that affects millions of individuals in the world today, with very low treatment options [1]. On the molecular level, AD is marked by the accumulation of aberrant deposits of β -amyloid peptides and tangled filaments called neurofibrillary tangles inside the neurons. These pathological markers are also associated with enhanced oxidative stress and drastic loss in acetylcholine, which is a neurotransmitter vital in learning and memory processes [2].

Although a lot of research has been done, there is as yet no recognized treatment that cures AD, and the existing treatment focuses mostly on symptom control. The strategy based on the cholinergic hypothesis, that is, more intensive cholinergic neurotransmission can help to solve the cognitive issues concerning the disease, is among the most employed treatment strategies. In this case, acetylcholinesterase (AChE) inhibitors play the most essential part by preventing the enzymatic degradation of acetylcholine (ACh), which consequently results in increased levels of acetylcholine in the synapses and also cholinergic brain performance [3]. The existing AChE inhibitors, such as Donepezil, Rivastigmine, Tacrine, and galantamine, provide symptomatic relief, but they are usually linked with minimal efficiency and side effects [4,5]. This underscores the focus on an important necessity gap in existing treatments that include the need to develop cholinesterase inhibitors with improved pharmacokinetic and safety profiles that are safer and more efficacious.

In addition to AChE, butyrylcholinesterase (BuChE) has recently emerged as a promising yet insufficiently understood target of therapeutic interest in AD. The activity of BChE is also discovered to be increased as the AD advances and mostly in late stages, when the concentration of AChE is reduced [6]. BuChE has a possible compensatory effect in the preservation of the cholinergic tones as well as contributing to the hydrolysis of ACh, and it has also been implicated in the aggregation of Amyloid- β and pathology of tau, so that its inhibition would have a two-fold benefit of not only improving the cholinergic neurotransmission but also reducing the neurodegenerative process [7]. Although this is an opportunity, there is limited research on dual AChE/BChE inhibitors, highlighting a major area in need of further investigation.

Amongst the recent chemical entities investigated for cholinesterase inhibition, the pyrimidine scaffolds gained much more interest for the development of cholinesterase inhibitors due to their versatility and extensive pharmacological profile, including anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, anticholinesterase, and neuroprotective properties. The pyrimidine ring is one of the privileged structures that display planarity and the ability to interact through hydrogen bonding, making it a suitable candidate to bind with the active site of AChE [8]. Sulphonyl groups have become of great interest to improve the biological potential of pyrimidinone derivatives. The presence of sulphonyl moieties enhances water solubility, metabolic stability, and bioavailability, which is a vital feature in the development of drugs that act on the central nervous system. They are also able to bind and interact via electrostatic and hydrogen bonding within the active site of AChE, which can enhance affinity and specificity of interaction [9]. It is believed that dual binding at the catalytic active site (CAS) and peripheral anionic site (PAS) of AChE is a strategic value and prevents ACh hydrolysis and could conciliate A β -aggregation in Alzheimer's disease. The presence of α , β -unsaturated carbonyl structure, which provides covalent or non-covalent interaction with cholinesterase enzymes, is significant because it contributes to enzyme inhibitory activity, anti-inflammatory and antioxidant activity of chalcone moiety [10]. Thus, the conjugation of pyrimidinone cores with the sulphonyl chalcone is expected to have synergistic effects on the cholinesterase enzymes, leading to an increase in the inhibitory action and specificity.

Nevertheless, these structural motifs-sulphonyl pyrimidinone linked with chalcone, have not yet been explored rationally in the design of dual ChE inhibitors. Based on these considerations, the current study objective to explore the research gap by designing, synthesizing, and screening a new series of Chalcone-linked sulphonyl pyrimidinone hybrids (see Figure 1), aiming to provide a valuable contribution in the development of prospective candidates in the management of Alzheimer's disease.

Figure 1: Drug-design strategies for the development of Chalcone-linked Sulphonyl pyrimidinone hybrids

2. Experimental Section

2.1 General Information

All the chemicals and solvents used in the synthesis were of analytical reagent (AR) grade and were purchased from Merck Chemicals, Loba Chemie, and CDH Chemicals. Acetylcholinesterase (from *Electrophorus electricus*), Butyrylcholinesterase, acetylcholine chloride, DTNB, and the chemicals for preparing the phosphate buffer were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich. Thin-layer chromatography (TLC) was performed on silica gel G (E. Merck), utilizing a mobile phase of chloroform and methanol in a ratio of 80:20, to monitor the progress and completion of the reaction. The melting point was determined using a melting point apparatus with open glass capillaries and is reported without correction. Structural characterization was carried out using a Bruker Advance Neo 400 MHz spectrometer to analyze both ¹H-NMR and ¹³C-NMR, with DMSO-d₆ as the solvent and tetramethylsilane (TMS) as the reference. Infrared (IR) spectra were recorded on a Perkin Elmer Spectrum FTIR spectrophotometer (Version 10.6.2), and mass spectra were obtained using an Xevo G2-XS QTOF mass spectrometer. Elemental analysis was conducted with an Elemental 2400 Elemental Analyzer in CHN mode.

2.2 Synthesis

General Procedure for synthesis of (E)-3-(4-substitutedphenyl)-1-phenylprop-2-en-1-one

(1a-f)

Synthesis of substituted chalcone was carried out by dissolving an equimolar amount of acetophenone (0.01 mol) and corresponding substituted benzaldehyde (0.01 mol) in 8-10 ml of absolute ethanol in a microwave-compatible sealed vessel. The solution was reduced alkaline by the dropwise addition of 50% aqueous sodium hydroxide solution. The reaction mixture was then microwaved with irradiation at a power of 350 W, maintaining the temperature at 70-75°C for 10-15 minutes. The progress of reaction completion was monitored by thin-layer chromatography (TLC) with ethanol: hexane (6:4). Upon completion, the reaction mixture was poured into ice-cold water and neutralized with dilute hydrochloric acid, resulting in the precipitation of the compound. The solid compound obtained was filtered, thoroughly washed with cold water, and dried. The chalcone derivatives yielded the desired compound (**1a-f**).

(E)-3-(4-chlorophenyl)-1-phenylprop-2-en-1-one(1a)

IR (KBr) (cm^{-1}): 3121.21-3081.56 (Ar C-H), 1690.46 (C=O), 1575.36 (C=C), 1445.46 (Ar C-H) (**S1**); ^1H NMR (δ ppm, 400 MHz, DMSO- d_6): 7.33-7.52 (5H, d, Ar-H), 7.53-7.79 (5H, m, Ar-H), 7.60 (1H, d, $\text{CH}=\underline{\text{C}}\text{H}$), 8.02 (1H, d, $\underline{\text{C}}\text{H}=\text{CH}$) (**S2**); ^{13}C NMR (δ ppm, 400MHz, DMSO- d_6) 121.36 (1C, $\text{CH}=\underline{\text{C}}\text{H}$), 127.34 (2C), 128.13 (2C), 128.54 (2C), 128.61 (2C), 128.82 (2C), 131.94 (1C), 134.94 (2C), 138.42 (1C), 144.62 (1C), 190.16 (1C) (**S3**).

General procedure for synthesis of (E)-3-(4-substitutedphenyl)-1-phenylprop-2-en-1-one

(2a-f)

Equimolar quantities of chalcone derivatives **1a-f** (0.01 mol) were taken in a microwave-compatible sealed vessel, and cold chlorosulphonic acid (0.05 mol) was added slowly with continuous stirring while maintaining the temperature below 5°C in an ice bath. The reaction mixture was then subjected to microwave irradiation at a power of 250 W for 5–8 min, ensuring a controlled temperature at 10-15°C during the initial addition. The reaction completion was monitored by TLC (ethyl acetate: hexane, 3:7); the mixture was carefully poured into crushed ice, leading to the formation of a solid precipitate, washed thoroughly

with cold water to remove excess acid, and recrystallized from ethanol to afford pure compounds (**2a-f**).

(E)-3-(4-chlorophenyl)-1-phenylprop-2-en-1-one(2a)

IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 3057.62 (Ar-CH), 1659.21 (C=O), 1589.92 (Ar-C=C), 1576.92 (C=C), 1487.53 (C-H), 1334.31 (C-S), 1173.62 (N-SO₂), 774.68 (S-Cl)(**S4**), ¹HNMR (δ ppm, 400 MHz, DMSO-d₆): 7.49-7.59 (5H, d, Ar-H), 7.66-8.02 (5H, m, 1.50 Hz, Ar-H), 7.62 (1H, d, CH=CH), 8.05 (1H, d, CH=CH) (**S5**); ¹³CNMR(δ ppm, 400MHz, DMSO-d₆) 121.35 (1C), 127.93 (2C), 129.12 (2C), 129.52 (2C), 130.41 (2C), 134.84 (1C), 134.96 (1C), 144.63 (1C) 151.83 (1C), 188.89 (1C)(**S6**).

General procedure for synthesis of (E)-N-carbamoyl-4-(3-(4-substitutedphenyl) acryloyl) benzenesulfonamide (3a-f)

An equimolar amount of compounds **2a-f** (0.01 mol) and urea (0.01 mol) was dissolved in a 10% aqueous sodium hydroxide solution. The reaction mixture was subjected to microwave irradiation at a power of 350 W, maintaining the temperature at 60-65°C for 10-15 minutes. Afterward, the reaction mixture was allowed to cool to room temperature and neutralized with dilute hydrochloric acid, resulting in the formation of a precipitate. The solid compound was collected by filtration, washed thoroughly with water, and dried to afford the final compounds (**3a-f**).

(E)-N-carbamoyl-4-(3-(4-chlorophenyl) acryloyl) benzenesulfonamide (3a)

IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 3441.89 (N-H), 3304.63 (NH₂), 1658.01 (C=O), 1600.78 (C=O, Urea), 1589.92(C=C), 1487.53 (Ar-C=C), 1309.85 (C-S), 1173.62 (N-SO₂) (**S7**), ¹HNMR (δ ppm, 400 MHz, DMSO-d₆): 6.73 (1H, s, NH₂), 6.74 (2H, NH₂), 7.31-7.53 (5H, m, Ar-CH), 7.61 (1H, d, CH=CH), 7.54-8.03 (4H, m, Ar-H), 8.03 (1H, d, CH=CH) (**S8**); ¹³CNMR(δ ppm, 400MHz, DMSO-d₆) 121.34(1C), 127.86 (2C), 128.11(2C) , 128.73 (2C), 130.42 (2C), 134.83(1C), 134.95 (1C), 136.12 (1C), 144.63 (1C), 156.42 (1C), 188.90 (1C) (**S9**).

General Procedure for Synthesis of (E)-1-((4-(3-(4-substitutedphenyl) acryloyl) phenyl) sulphonyl) pyrimidine-2, 4, 6(1H, 3H, 5H)-trione(4a-f)

A small piece of sodium metal was added to absolute ethanol (EtOH) in a microwave-compatible reaction vessel under an inert atmosphere, which completely dissolved to form sodium ethoxide. After complete dissolution, diethyl malonate was added to the solution with

stirring. The reaction mixture was then added with the ethanolic solution of the desired compound (3a-f). The sealed reaction vessel was then placed in a microwave synthesizer and irradiated at 100 °C with controlled pressure for 15-30 min (at level 5, for 3 cycles) while continuously stirred. After completion of the microwave irradiation, the reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature, resulting in a white solid. To recover the crystalline compound, the white solid was treated with hot water and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. The resulting crystalline product was filtered, washed with cold water, and dried.

(E)-1-((4-(3-(4-chlorophenyl) acryloyl) phenyl) sulphonyl) pyrimidine-2, 4, 6(1H, 3H, 5H)-trione (4a)

Light yellow powder; m.p. 170-172 °C; IR(KBr, cm⁻¹): 3422.74-3348.36 (N-H), 1684.31 (C=O), 1617.22(C=O), 1592.84(C=C), 1528.32 (Ar-C=C), 1444.52 (Ar-C=C), 1322.45 (C-S), 1283.66 (C-N), 1174.65 (N-SO₂), 1130.62 (S=O), 760.72 (C-Cl) (**S10**), ¹HNMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ 3.52 (2H, d, CH₂), 6.71 (2H, d, Ar-H), 7.47-7.54 (5H, m, J= 3.05Hz, Ar-H), 7.76 (2H, d, Ar-H), 8.02 (1H,d, J=1.50hz, CH=CH), 7.78 (1H, J=2.0Hz, CH=CH) (**S11**), ¹³CNMR(400MHz, DMSO-d₆), δppm: 39.73 (1C), 121.35(1C), 127.82 (2C), 128.72 (2C), 129.15 (2C), 130.23 (2C), 133.82 (1C), 134.62 (1C), 134.92 (1C), 136.42 (1C), 144.16 (1C), 151.03 (1C), 166.42 (1C), 169.61 (1C), 188.96 (1C) (**S12**), MS m/z: 432.72 [M⁺] (**S13**); Elemental Anal. Calcd for C₁₉H₁₃ClN₂O₆S: C, 57.82; H, 3.74; Cl, 1.12; N, 6.61; O, 23.66; S, 7.06; Found: C, 57.39; H, 3.24; Cl, 1.42; N, 6.18; O, 23.27; S, 6.87.

(E)-1-((4-(3-(4-hydroxyphenyl) acryloyl) phenyl) sulphonyl) pyrimidine-2,4,6(1H,3H,5H)-trione(4b)

Light yellow powder; m.p. 183-185 °C; IR(KBr, cm⁻¹): 3433.33 (N-H), 3350.03 (O-H), 2925.32 (Ar C-H), 1707.42 (C=O), 1617.75 (C=O), 1591.74(C=C), 1514.39 (Ar-C=C), 1444.52 (Ar-C=C), 1294.56 (C-N), 1171.17 (N-SO₂), 1129.44 (S=O) (**S14**), ¹HNMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ 3.53 (2H, d, CH₂), 6.70 (2H, d, J=0.40Hz, Ar-H), 7.50-7.65 (5H, m, J=1.50Hz, Ar-H), 7.76 (2H, d, J=2.23Hz, Ar-H), 7.54 (1H,J=0.40Hz, Ar-CH=CH-Ar), 8.02 (1H,J=1.90Hz, Ar-CH=CH-Ar) (**S15**), ¹³CNMR(400MHz, DMSO-d₆): δppm: 39.73(1C), 115.92 (2C), 121.35 (1C,CH=CH), 127.84 (2C), 128.12 (2C), 130.23 (2C), 130.92 (2C), 134.93 (1C), 136.42 (1C), 144.16 (1C, CH=CH), 151.03 (1C, C=O), 158.21 (1C, HO-C₆H₄), 166.46 (1C, C=O), 169.61(1C, C=O), 188.96 (1C, C=O) (**S16**). MS m/z: 415.05 [M⁺] (**S17**), Elemental Anal. Calcd for C₁₉H₁₄N₂O₇S: C, 55.07; H, 3.41; N, 6.76; O, 27.03; S, 7.74; Found: C, 54.84; H, 3.12; N, 6.26; O, 26.78; S, 7.37.

(E)-1-((4-(3-(4-nitrophenyl) acryloyl) phenyl) sulphonyl) pyrimidine-2, 4, 6(1H,3H,5H)-trione(4c)

Color: Dark orange powder; m.p. 168-170 °C; IR(KBr, cm⁻¹): 3429.99 (N-H), 1694.54 (C=O), 1617.88 (C=O), 1592.86 (C=C), 1526.79 (Ar-C=C), 1446.56 (Ar-C=C), 1235.42 (C-N), 1175.54 (N-SO₂), 1131.96 (S=O)(S18), ¹HNMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ 3.35 (2H, d, CH₂), 7.01 (2H, d, J=1.54Hz, Ar-H), 7.74-7.92 (5H, m, J=1.52 Hz, Ar-H), 7.95 (2H, d, J=0.40Hz, Ar-H), 7.73 (1H, d, J=2.23Hz, CH=CH), 8.04 (1H, d, J=1.90Hz, CH=CH) (S19), ¹³CNMR(400MHz, DMSO-d₆): δppm: 39.74 (1C), 121.33 (1C,CH=CH), 123.34(1C), 124.23 (2C), 127.82(2C), 129.13(2C), 130.46(2C), 134.92(1C), 136.47(1C), 144.17 (1C, CH=CH), 147.36 (1C), 151.07(1C=O), 166.48(1C, C=O), 169.64(1C, C=O), 188.94(1C, C=O) (S20); MS m/z: 444.05 [M⁺] (S21);Elemental Anal. Calcd for C₁₉H₁₃N₃O₈S: C, 51.47; H, 2.96; N, 9.48; O, 28.87; S, 7.23; Found: C, 51.86;1 H, 3.17; N, 9.91; O, 29.08; S, 7.54.

(E)-1-((4-(3-(p-tolyl) acryloyl) phenyl) sulphonyl) pyrimidine-2,4,6(1H,3H,5H)-trione (4d)

Color: Yellowish white powder; m.p. 172-175 °C; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 3422.89 (N-H), 1617.29 (C=O), 1527.51 (C=C), 1444.59 (Ar-C=C), 1213.71 (C-N), 1132.83 (S=O), 1173.79 (N-SO₂), 1132.83 (S=O), 1086.74 (Ar C-C) (S22);¹HNMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ 2.28 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.35 (2H, d, CH₂), 7.25-7.66 (5H, m, J=2.23Hz, 0.40 Hz, Ar-H), 7.76-8.03 (4H, m, J=1.52Hz, Ar-H), 7.59 (1H, d, J=2.21Hz, CH=CH), 8.05 (1H, d, J=0.52Hz, CH=CH) (S23); ¹³CNMR(400MHz, DMSO-d₆),δppm: 21.42 (1C), 39.74 (1C), 121.35(1C), 127.78 (2C), 128.14 (2C), 128.54 (2C), 129.43 (2C), 130.46 (2C), 134.89 (1C), 136.44 (1C), 137.72 (1C), 144.24 (1C), 151.08(1C, C=O), 166.47(1C, C=O), 169.64(1C, C=O), 188.92 (1C, C=O) (S24); MS m/z: 414.15 [M⁺] (S25), Elemental Anal. Calcd for C₂₀H₁₆N₂O₆S: C, 58.25; H, 3.91; N, 6.79; O, 23.28; S, 7.77; Found: C, 57.97; H, 3.43; N, 6.23; O, 22.97; S, 7.21.

(E)-1-((4-(3-(4-isopropylphenyl)acryloyl)phenyl)sulphonyl)pyrimidine-2,4,6(1H,3H,5H)-trione (4e)

Color: yellowish white powder; m.p. 162-164 °C; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 3422.74 (N-H), 3011.34 (Ar C-H), 1659.01 (C=O), 1600.78 (C=O), 1588.95(C=C), 1565.47 (Ar-C=C), 1446.48 (Ar-C=C), 1333.33 (C-S), 1213.71 (C-N), 1106. 93 (S=O), 1173.62 (N-SO₂), 1091.74 (Ar C-C) (S26); ¹HNMR(DMSO-d₆, 400 MHz), δppm: 1.20 (6H, d, CH₃), 2.82 (1H, m, CH), 3.35 (2H, d, CH₂), 6.75 (1H, d, J=2.23 Hz, Ar-H), 7.31 (2H, m, J=0.42 Hz, Ar-H), 7.59 (1H,d, J=2.21 Hz, CH=CH), 7.60-8.01 (4H, m, J=1.52 Hz, Ar-H), 8.03 (1H, d, J=0.52 Hz, CH=CH) (S27);

^{13}C NMR (DMSO, 400MHz): δ_{ppm} : 23.93 (2C, CH_3), 33.87 (1C), 39.74 (1C), 121.32 (1C, $\text{CH}=\underline{\text{C}}\text{H}$), 126.34(2C), 126.91(2C), 127.82 (2C), 128.14(1C), 130.42(2C), 134.92(1C), 136.47(1C), 144.23 (1C, $\underline{\text{C}}\text{H}=\text{CH}$), 147.12 (2C), 151.07(1C, $\text{C}=\text{O}$), 166.47(1C, $\text{C}=\text{O}$), 169.64(1C, $\text{C}=\text{O}$), 188.92 (1C, $\text{C}=\text{O}$) (**S28**); MS m/z : 443.05 [M^+] (**S29**). Elemental Anal. Calcd for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_2\text{O}_6\text{S}$: C, 59.99; H, 4.58; N, 6.36; O, 21.79; S, 7.28; Found: C, 59.38; H, 4.15; N, 6.02; O, 21.26; S, 6.98.

(E)-1-((4-(3-(4-methoxyphenyl)acryloyl)phenyl)sulphonyl)pyrimidine-2,4,6(1H,3H,5H)-trione (4f)

Color: off-white powder; m.p. 167-169 °C; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 3422.74 (N-H), 3011.34 (Ar C-H), 1658.01 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$), 1601.72 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$), 1588.95($\text{C}=\text{C}$), 1565.48 (Ar-C=C), 1446.42 (Ar-C=C), 1333.33 (C-S), 1213.71 (C-N), 1106.93 (S=O), 1173.62 (N-SO₂), 1091.74 (Ar C-C) (**S29**); ^1H NMR(DMSO- d_6 , 400 MHz), δ_{ppm} : 3.80 (3H, s, CH_3), 6.75 (1H, d, $J=2.23$ Hz, Ar-H), 7.32 (2H, m, $J=0.42$ Hz, Ar-H), 7.59 (1H, d, $J=2.21$ Hz, $\text{CH}=\underline{\text{C}}\text{H}$), 7.62-8.02 (4H, m, $J=1.52$ Hz, Ar-H), 8.06 (1H, d, $J=0.52$ Hz, $\underline{\text{C}}\text{H}=\text{CH}$) (**S30**); ^{13}C NMR (DMSO, 400MHz): δ_{ppm} : 55.8 (1C, $-\text{OCH}_3$), 121.33 (1C, $\text{CH}=\underline{\text{C}}\text{H}$), 126.32 (2C), 126.91(2C), 127.83 (2C), 128.14(1C), 130.41 (2C), 134.91 (1C), 136.47 (1C), 144.23 (1C, $\underline{\text{C}}\text{H}=\text{CH}$), 147.12 (2C), 151.07 (1C, $\text{C}=\text{O}$), 166.47(1C, $\text{C}=\text{O}$), 169.64(1C, $\text{C}=\text{O}$), 188.92 (1C, $\text{C}=\text{O}$) (**S31**); MS m/z : 443.05 [M^+] (**S29**). Elemental Anal. Calcd for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{O}_6\text{S}$: C, 58.25; H, 3.91; N, 6.79; O, 23.28; S, 7.77; Found: C, 58.31; H, 4.06; N, 6.87; O, 23.34; S, 7.88.

2.3 Biological Activities

2.3.1 *in-vitro* Acetylcholinesterase Inhibitory Activity

The screening of *in-vitro* acetylcholinesterase inhibitory activity was determined by using Ellman's method [14] on both AChE and BuChE enzymes through UV-visible spectroscopy. An assay solution, containing 1 ml 0.1 M phosphate buffer (pH 8.0), 50 μL of the test compounds in six different concentrations (25, 50, 75, 100, 125 and 150 nM) and 50 μL of enzyme solution (AChE from *Electrophorus electricus* or BuChE from equine serum both at 2U/mL) was pre-incubated at 37°C for 15 minutes. After the pre-incubation period, the reaction was initiated by adding μL of DTNB (5, 5'-dithiobis-(2-nitrobenzoic acid), 0.01M), and 20 μL of the substrate (acetylcholine chloride for AChE or butyrylthiocholine iodide for BChE assay). The enzymatic activity was measured by taking the absorbance at 412 nm for 5 minutes using a UV spectrophotometer. A control and blank without the test compound and

enzyme, respectively, were run in parallel. The percentage inhibition was determined using the absorbance values through the formula $[(Ac-As)/Ac] \times 100$ and the determinations of IC_{50} value were done using the dose-response curve. All the measurements were conducted three times, and the results were represented as mean and SEM. This test determined the ability of the compound to inhibit AChE and BuChE, which shows that it has therapeutic implications for neurodegenerative ailments.

2.5 Experimental Animals

The in-vivo experiment was performed using Swiss albino (2 months old, 25-30g of both sexes) mice, which were the source of Sainath Agencies in Hyderabad. The Institutional Animal Ethics Committee of Shri Rawatpura Sarkar Institute of Pharmacy (Reg. No. SRIP/IAEC/2022 23/B/03) gave the ethical approval. The institute is a part of CSVTU, Chhattisgarh, and the practice is in accordance with CPCSEA in New Delhi. The mice were placed in colony cages where they were free to feed on normal feeds and drink water. Environmental parameters were a 12-light/ dark cycle at room temperature and 50 -5 humidity. To reduce stress and have credible results, they were introduced to the laboratory setting over five days. The experimental design included six animals per group, comprised of three males and three females.

2.5.1 Neurotoxicity Study

Motor function in mice was evaluated using the standard rotarod test. In this test, mice were trained to maintain their balance on a knurled plastic rod, which is 1 inch in diameter and 25 cm high, rotating at 6 rpm for 1 minute. Only those mice that completed the training were selected for the study. The mice then received test compounds through intraperitoneal injection at doses of 100 mg/kg and 300 mg/kg. Neurotoxicity was defined as the inability to remain on the rotarod for at least 1 minute across three consecutive trials. [15].

2.5.2 Cognitive enhancement activity

Based on *in-vitro* acetylcholinesterase inhibitory activity, compounds **4d** and **4e** were chosen to be subjected to behavioral analysis on a scopolamine-induced animal model in the Y-Maze. Mice were randomly divided into four groups (n=6 per group): control group vehicle, 20 mL/Kg), positive control group (Donepezil, 5mg/Kg), and two treatment groups, which received compounds **4d** and **4e**, each group was orally administered a single dose (5 mg/kg) through oral gavage in the form of suspension 30 minutes before testing. Cognitive

performance was assessed using the Y-maze apparatus, consisting of three identical arms arranged at a 120° angle. The cognitive-enhancing effect was assessed via two key parameters: percentage alteration and latency to find reward. Mice were placed individually at the center of the maze and allowed to explore freely for 8 minutes. The sequence and number of arm entries without repetition (e.g., ABC, BCA) were recorded to calculate the percentage alteration using the formula $\% \text{ alteration behavior} = (\text{number of alterations} / \text{total number of arm entries} - 2) \times 100$, where higher alteration indicates improved spatial working memory [16]. Simultaneously, a food reward was always in one arm, and the time in seconds to first arrive at the reward arm was recorded, with a shorter time showing a better memory-based navigation. The maze was washed using 70 percent ethanol to remove olfactory cues after each trial was over [17]. The combination of these activities can provide useful data regarding the cognitive performance of the animal and can be applied to test the impact of various compounds on cognitive performance.

2.6 Molecular docking studies

Molecular docking simulation algorithms predict interactions and binding affinities between ligands and target proteins. This approach facilitates the optimization of molecular structures and the identification of potential lead compounds for therapeutic development [18]. The two-dimensional (2D) chemical structures of the synthesized sulphonyl pyrimidinone derivatives (**4a-f**) and the standard drug Donepezil were obtained using ChemDraw 22.2.0.2.0. These 2D structures were then imported into ChemDraw 3D 22.2.0.2.0 to generate their corresponding three-dimensional (3D) models. The 2D structures were opened in Chem 3D, where energy minimization of each ligand was carried out using the MM2 force field to obtain stable, optimized conformations. The resulting 3D structures were saved in the Protein Data Bank (.pdb) format for subsequent molecular docking studies [19]. The crystal structures of the target enzymes were obtained from the RCSB Protein Data Bank (PDB); they can be accessed directly at the following URL (<http://www.rscb.org/pdb>). The recombinant human acetylcholinesterase in complex with Donepezil (PDB ID: 4EY7; resolution: 2.35 Å; chain A), and human butyrylcholinesterase (BChE) in complex with N-((1-(2, 3-dihydro-1H-inden-2-yl) piperidin-3-yl) methyl)-N-(2-methoxyethyl)-2-naphthamide (PDB ID: 4TPK; resolution: 2.70 Å; chain A) [20].

Molecular docking simulations were performed using Molegro Virtual Docker (MVD) v.6.0. The software features an integrated cavity detection algorithm that is automatic in the

detection of the potential binding cavities within a defined search space of $30 \times 30 \times 30 \text{ \AA}^3$. This identification of cavities process instructs the docking algorithm to the appropriate areas of the protein structure during the simulation stage. In both target proteins, five different binding sites were identified (Figure 2). Among these, the site of the largest volume and surface area was chosen as the primary binding site for molecular docking analysis, as summarized in Table 1. Molecular docking simulations were conducted using the MolDock SE (Simplex Evolution) search algorithm, and binding affinities were evaluated using the MolDock scoring function at a grid resolution of 0.30 \AA . The defined X, Y, and Z coordinates (Table 1) were used to centrally position a spherical search with 15.0 to cover the selected binding pocket. Molecular docking analysis was carried out in order to ensure comprehensive sampling, by using a population of 50 and 10 independent runs per ligand, each with 1500 iterations to sample the entire surface of the identified active binding site of the target protein [21]. Interaction of the protein-ligand complex with the target proteins was performed using the PyMOL 2.4.0 software to visualize the molecular surface of the binding pocket [22].

Table 1. Values of the binding site of the target proteins.

Protein Target	PDB ID	Volume (\AA^3)	Surface Area (\AA^2)	X-Center	Y-Center	Z-Center
Acetylcholinesterase	4EY7	172.544	459.52	-0.94	-38.30	33.65
Butyrylcholinesterase	4TPK	418.304	913.92	-2.95	8.79	16.76

Figure 2: Predicted target protein binding pocket: (A) PDB ID: 4EY7, and (B) PDB ID: 4TPK. The protein structures are represented in cartoon form, displayed in blue and red, whereas the binding cavities identified are highlighted in green.

2.6.3 Drug likeness and BBB permeability analysis

The drug-likeness and physicochemical properties of the synthesized compounds (**4a-e**) were comprehensively assessed by using computational tools like Swiss ADME (<http://www.swissadme.ch/>), which was employed to predict key physicochemical parameters, including Molecular weight, hydrogen bond donors (HBD), hydrogen bond acceptor (HBA), rotatable bonds (RB), lipophilicity (Log P), and topological polar surface area (TPSA). Further to assess the drug-likeness and BBB permeability, the Molsoft tool (<https://www.molsoft.com/>) and the BBB predictor (<https://www.cbligand.org/BBB/>) were used, respectively.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Chemistry

The synthesis of sulphonyl pyrimidinone derivatives (**4a-f**) was achieved through a multistep process via microwave assisted method mentioned in Scheme 1. The formation of chalcone (**1a-f**) was confirmed by the appearance of IR stretching peaks near $3121-3081\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Ar-C-H), 1575.36 cm^{-1} (conjugated C=C), and 1690.46 cm^{-1} (carbonyl $>\text{C}=\text{O}$). The synthesized chalcone structure was further supported by the ^1H NMR peaks that appeared for aromatic proton signals (m, δ 7.35-7.54 ppm) and aliphatic proton signal (d, 7.60 ppm and 8.01 ppm) along with ^{13}C NMR peaks, i.e., for ethylene carbon within 144.62 ppm (Ar- $\underline{\text{C}}\text{H}=\text{CH}$ -) and 121.36 ppm (Ar- $\text{CH}=\underline{\text{C}}\text{H}$ -CO), and 190.16 ppm spectra for carbonyl carbon. The subsequent Chlorosulphonation of substituted chalcones (**1a-f**) yielded the corresponding chalcone sulphonyl chlorides (**2a-e**). The addition of the sulphonyl chloride group was confirmed by the spectral peaks for sulphonyl at 1173.62 cm^{-1} (S=O) and 1334.31 cm^{-1} (C-S) in addition to the appearance of a spectral spike for aromatic carbon-bearing sulphonyl (Ar- $\underline{\text{C}}_4$ -SO₂Cl) group at 151.83 ppm in ^{13}C NMR spectra. The formation of sulphonylurea derivatives (**3a-f**) was supported by the IR spectra at 1600.01 cm^{-1} for urea carbonyl and 3441.89 cm^{-1} , 3304.63 cm^{-1} peak for amines of urea. The attachment of urea with sulphonyl was further confirmed by the chemical shift of ^1H NMR spectra around 6.73 ppm for amine groups and ^{13}C NMR spectral peak at 156.42 ppm (C=O) of urea. The cyclization has been done to attain the final compounds (**4a-f**) were characterized by the ^{13}C NMR spectral data. The appearance of chemical shift values at 39.74 ppm for the cyclic CH₂ group and 166.47 ppm and 169.64 ppm for the carbonyl group of the pyrimidinone ring concluded the cyclization in compounds (**4a-f**).

Scheme 1: General synthetic route for the synthesis of sulphonyl Pyrimidinone Derivatives

Reagent and Reaction conditions: a) EtOH, 50% NaOH, MW irradiated at 350 W and 70–75°C for 10–15 minutes, (b) ClSO₃H, MW irradiated at 250 W for 5–8 min at controlled temperature 10–15°C, (c) urea, 10%NaOH, MW irradiated at 350 W, 60–65°C for 10–15 min. (d) EtONa, diethyl malonate, MW irradiated at 280 W, 100 °C for 15–30 min (3 cycles).

3.2 *In-vitro* Anti-acetylcholinesterase activity

The synthesized compounds **4a–f** were evaluated for their inhibitory activity against both the acetylcholinesterase (AChE) and butyrylcholinesterase (BChE). The IC₅₀ values for AChE inhibition ranged from 31.66 nM to 98.66 nM and for BuChE inhibition from 33.33 nM to 93.33 nM (See Figure 3 and Table 2). These were compared with the standard AChE inhibitor Donepezil (AChE IC₅₀ = 51.66 nM, BuChE IC₅₀ = 59.00 nM). The results revealed that substitution at the para position of the aromatic ring significantly influenced enzyme inhibition. Among all, compound **4d** (4-CH₃) and **4e** (4-CH(CH₃)₂) exhibited the most potent dual inhibitory activity (AChE inhibition; IC₅₀ = 31.66±0.882 nM and 37.33±1.453 nM, BuChE IC₅₀ = 33.33±0.882 nM and 34.00±1.528 nM respectively), surpassing the standard in both assays, it is indicative of the complimentary impact of a hydrophobic electron-donating methyl and Isopropyl group on binding affinity of enzymes. The polar hydroxyl-substituted compound **4b** (4-OH) also showed moderate dual inhibition, indicating that the presence and

nature of the substituent are critical for activity, as well as hydroxyl substituent and unsubstituted are still tolerated but less effective than alkyl groups. In contrast, compounds bearing electron-withdrawing groups (4a-Cl, 4c-NO₂) displayed significantly reduced inhibition of enzymes, likely due to steric hindrance or unfavorable electronic effects. Overall, the data suggest that small lipophilic electron-donating groups at the para position favor dual cholinesterase inhibition, with compounds 4d and 4e emerging as the most promising leads for further development in the treatment of neurodegenerative disorders such as Alzheimer's disease.

Figure 3: *In-vitro* anti-AChE and anti-BuChE potential of compound (4a-f). All values are expressed in mean ± SEM, n=3. One-way ANOVA and Dunnett test were performed for statistical analysis. Data indicates *p>0.05, **P< 0.05, *** p<0.001, and ns indicates not significant when compared to the standard. IC₅₀ Value expressed in μM ± SEM, Standard: Donepezil (DNZ) used as the standard AChE inhibitor.

Table 2: Antiacetylcholinesterase and Antioxidant Potential of Sulphonyl Pyrimidinone Derivatives (4a-f).

S. No.	Compound	R	IC ₅₀ Value ^a	
			eelAChE	BChE
1.	^b Standard	-	51.66±0.882	59.00±0.577
2.	4a	4-Cl	77.33±0.882	67.66±1.202
3.	4b	4-OH	57.33±1.453	53.00±0.577
4.	4c	4-NO ₂	98.66±1.764	93.33±0.882
5.	4d	4-CH ₃	31.66±0.882	33.33±0.882
6.	4e	4-CH(CH ₃) ₂	37.33±1.453	34.00±1.528
7.	4f	4-OCH ₃	63.66±1.453	55.66±1.202

^a IC₅₀ Value expressed in nM±SEM

^b Standard: Donepezil (DNZ) is used as the standard AChE inhibitor, and Ascorbic Acid as the Standard antioxidant agent

3.4 Neurotoxicity Study

The neurotoxicity of the synthesized pyrimidinone derivatives, administered at doses of 100 and 300 mg/kg i.p., caused dose-dependent neurotoxicity in the rotarod test. At the higher dose (300 mg/kg), mice demonstrated a significant motor impairment, with less than half animals in a group treated with compounds **4d** and **4e** failing to stay on the rod for one minute in multiple trials, indicating a little neurotoxic effect. In contrast, the animals treated with 100 mg/kg did not show noticeable impairment. These results suggested that higher doses lead to a minor motor dysfunction, and further studies are needed to investigate the mechanisms of action and the compound's safety profile at lower doses.

3.5 Behavioral Study

The effects of synthesized compounds **4d** and **4e**, along with the standard drug Donepezil, on cognitive function were assessed using the Y-maze task to evaluate spatial learning and working memory. The findings presented a detailed comparison of the improvements on cognitive effects of the compounds compared to the standard treatment. Group I (Control group) reflected an intrinsic change of 46.17 ± 0.978 and a latency to locate the reward of 36.00 ± 0.577 sec. Conversely, Group II (scopolamine-treated) exhibited a strong decrease in spontaneous alteration (35.51 ± 1.155 %) and prolonged latency to obtain reward (54.83 ± 0.601 sec.), which is a sign of impairment of cognition by scopolamine. Group III (treated with Donepezil) showed large recovery rates, as it had a high spontaneous alteration (62.07 ± 1.768 %) and low latency (29.00 ± 0.365 sec.) when compared to the disease group (Group II), which proved the effectiveness of Donepezil as a cognitive-enhancing agent. Group V (tested on compound **4e**) also showed a better spontaneous change (55.72 ± 1.223 %) and latency (29.16 ± 0.477 sec.) compared to the disease group, with a marginal difference between Donepezil and compound **4d**. The outcomes of the study suggest that the test compounds **4d** and **4e** can effectively ameliorate scopolamine-induced cognitive deficits, with compound **4d** emerging as a prominent candidate. Statistical analysis confirmed significant differences across all groups ($p < 0.05$) (**Figure 4**), supporting the therapeutic potential of **4d** and **4e** in cognitive disorders. The data are presented in **Table 3**.

Table 3: % Spontaneous Alteration and Latency Time to find Reward

Group	Treatment	% Spontaneous alteration	Latency Time ^a
Group-I (Control)	Normal Saline 20 ml/kg	46.17±0.978	36.00±0.577
Group-II (Disease)	Scopolamine (0.5mg/kg)	35.51±1.155	54.83±0.601
Group-III (Standard)	Scopolamine (0.5 mg/kg) +Donepezil (5mg/kg)	55.68±1.031	31.66±0.422
Group-IV (test)	Scopolamine (0.5mg/kg) +4d (5mg/kg)	62.07±1.768	29.00±0.365
Group-V (test)	Scopolamine (0.5 mg/kg) + 4e (5mg/kg)	55.72±1.223	29.16±0.477

^a Latency Time: Represent the time taken to find reward and values were expressed in second±SEM, n=6

Figure 4: Spatial learning and memory test of Sulphonyl Pyrimidinone Derivatives (4a-e) on Scopolamine-induced animal model by using Y-Maze. All values were expressed in mean±SEM, n=6, Data was analyzed by One way of ANOVA, using Tukeys t-test for statistical analysis. Data indicates #p<0.05 and ##P< 0.01 when compared to Donepezil, and *** p<0.001 indicates significant when compared to Control.

3.6 Molecular Docking Study

The synthesized sulphonyl pyrimidinone derivatives (4a-f) and reference drug Donepezil were docked with the active site of human acetylcholinesterase (AChE, PDB ID: 4EY7) and butyrylcholinesterase (BChE, PDB ID: 4TPK) using Molegro Virtual Docker version 6.0 software. The docking analysis using the MolDock scoring function demonstrated that all the synthesized compounds exhibited strong binding affinities in the active sites of the enzymes. The MolDock scores were between -116.569 kcal/mol and to -171.989 kcal/mol, which depicted favorable interactions between the ligands and target proteins. Out of the

synthesized sulphonyl pyrimidinones, the lowest score of MolDock was recorded on compound 4d demonstrating the highest binding affinity with the target enzymes. Compound 4d has a binding affinity of -171.989 kcal/mol with AChE and -157.214 kcal/mol with BChE, which is better than all the other ligands tested. Nevertheless, the reference agonist Donepezil showed a reduced MolDock score of -119.089 kcal/mol with AChE and -126.454 kcal/mol with BuChE, indicating a comparatively unstable ligand-receptor interaction. These observations offer the promising nature of compound 4d as a dual cholinesterase inhibitor. The binding affinity, number of H-bonds, and S-bond interaction of all the designed ligands were summarized in Table 4. The docking outcomes indicated that the increased binding affinities of all these compounds are mainly due to the formation of non-covalent interactions, including hydrogen bonding, π π stacking, and contact of the sulfur molecule with key amino acid residues at the active site of enzymes. It is important to note that the best binding profile was found in compound 4d, which has the lowest binding score compared to that of Donepezil. This is due to the best orientation and geometry of interaction in the binding pocket, hence strongly stabilizing the ligand protein complex. The Tyr124 and Tyr133 residues of acetylcholinesterase (AChE) were reported to be significant binding determinants among many interactions. These residues were also active in the formation of hydrogen bonds with all of the synthesized compounds, and with Donepezil, indicating a central position in the recognition and stabilization of the ligand in the AChE active site. The ongoing association of Tyr133 and Tyr124 amino acid residues stresses their position as a conserved binding site in the peripheral anionic site of acetylcholinesterase. Stunningly, the two residues also play a role in the regulation of β -amyloid aggregation, which could be through hydrogen bonding and 6 interactions, which are needed to stabilize or destabilize the establishment of amyloid fibrils.

Also, compound 4d had a strong steric contact with other essential residues such as Leu130, Tyr133, Gly116, and Gly117. These residues have been found to participate in the binding of substrates and catalysis, which implies that the presence of compound 4d mimics the natural substrate in the active site gorge of the enzymes of AChE. Figure 5 depicts that compound 4d and Donepezil have the same pattern of interaction with Thr120 through hydrogen bonds, and it shows that both are anchored using an identical mechanism in the BChE active site. These interactions, especially with Thr120, are conserved and indicate the binding capacity and structural stability of the synthesized derivatives. The molecular surface view illustrates the binding pocket interactions of compound **4d** and reference drug Donepezil with target

proteins, as shown in Figure 6. These findings further validate the rational design of the sulphonyl pyrimidinone scaffold as dual inhibition of cholinesterase enzymes. Among the tested compounds, compound **4d** consistently displayed the strongest binding affinities against both enzymes, AChE and BChE, reinforcing its potential as a lead molecule for the development against Alzheimer's disease.

Figure 5. Protein-ligand interaction of compound **4d** and Donepezil with the target proteins (A) acetylcholinesterase (AChE) and (B) butyrylcholinesterase (BChE). The blue dotted lines indicate the H-bond, while the red dotted line represents the S-bond interaction.

Figure 6: The binding pocket interaction of the compound **4d** and Donepezil with target proteins (A) acetylcholinesterase (AChE) and (B) butyrylcholinesterase (BChE) in molecular surface view.

Table 4: Molecular docking simulations of synthesized sulphonyl pyrimidone derivatives (**4a-f**) and donepezil with target proteins.

Compound ID	AChE (PDB ID: 4EY7)				BChE (PDB ID: 4TPK)			
	MolDock Score (kcal/mol)	No. of H-bond	H-bond Interaction	S-bond Interaction	MolDock Score (kcal/mol)	No. of H-bond	H-bond Interaction	S-bond Interaction
Donepezil	-119.089	2	Tyr 124, Tyr 133	Trp86, Gly120, Gly121, Gly122, Gly126, Leu130, Tye133, Ser203, Trp236, Phe297, His447	-126.454	3	Gly117, Thr120, Ser198	Gly116, Gly117
4a	-118.457	5	Tyr124, Ser203	Trp86, Pro88, Gly126, Leu130, Tye133, Ser203, His447	-119.457	2	Thr122, Tyr128	Gly117, Gly121, Leu125,
4b	-121.775	3	Ser129,	Gln71,	-123.952	3	Gly115,	Gly115,

			Tyr124, Ser203	Trp86, Pro88, Ala127, Gly126, Leu130, Tyr133, Ser203, His447,			Tyr128,	Gly117 Gly121 Tyr128, Glu197, Tyr332
4c	-117.556	4	Asn89, Arg90, Tyr124, Ser129,	Trp86, Val68, Gly122, Ala127, Leu130, Ser203	-116.569	3	Gly115, Thr122, Tyr128,	Gly115, Gly121 Thr122, Tyr128, Tyr332
4d	-171.989	2	Tyr124, Ser203	Val68, Gln71, Trp86, Asn87, Pro88, Ala127, Leu130, Ser203	-157.214	2	Thr120, Ala328	Gln67, Asn68, Trp82, Pro84, Ala328, His438
4e	-165.956	2	Tyr124, Asp74	Val68, Gln71, Trp86, Asn87, Pro88, Ala127, Leu130, Ser203	-144.654	1	Thr120	Asn68, Thr120, Glu197
4f	-152.101	3	Tyr124, Tyr133, Ala231	Val68, Gln71, Trp86, Asn87, Pro88, Ala127, Leu130, Ser203, Gly230, Ala231, Tyr337, Phe338,	-142.378	3	Asn68 Thr120, Ser198	Asn68, Gly116, Gln119, Pro285S

AChE: acetylcholinesterase; BChE: butyrylcholinesterase; H-bond: Hydrogen bond; S-bond: Steric bond

3.6.3 Drug likeness and BBB permeability analysis

The physicochemical and druglikeness properties of all synthesized compounds (**4a-e**) were evaluated using computational tools SwissADME and Molsoft, whereas BBB permeability was evaluated by using the BBB predictor. All the compounds follow Lipinski's rule with zero violation (Table 4) and show favorable lipophilicity (clogP) ranging from 0.55-2.20,

suggesting greater membrane permeability. The TPSA values for compounds **4a**, **4d**, and **4e** (126.07) are ideal for blood-brain barrier (BBB) penetration, while **4c** (171.89) has a higher TPSA than 140.0, which potentially limits its BBB permeability. Compounds (**4a-e**) exhibit drug likeness scores above 0.1 and also demonstrate promising BBB permeability, with scores ranging from 0.073 to 0.131, which are within the favorable range (≥ 0.02). From the above study, it was found that the synthesized compounds show good physicochemical and drug likeness properties. In terms of drug likeness and BBB penetration results, this pharmacophore model was found to be a potent structure to give optimum CNS-targeted activity.

Table 5: *In-silico* Drug likeness and Blood-Brain Barrier Permeability Analysis of Sulphonyl Pyrimidinone Derivatives (**4a-f**)

Compound	M w ^a	HBD ^a	HBA ^a	cLog P ^a	Rotable Bond ^a	TPSA ^a	Drug likeness ^b	BBB score ^c
4a	432.83	1	6	1.79	5	126.07	0.16	0.092
4b	414.39	2	7	0.86	5	146.30	0.30	0.073
4c	443.39	1	8	0.55	6	171.89	0.14	0.131
4d	412.42	1	6	1.57	5	126.07	0.22	0.127
4e	440.10	1	6	2.20	6	126.07	0.34	0.096
4f	428.42	1	7	1.28	5	126.07	0.11	0.076
DNZ	379.49	0	4	4.50	6	38.77	0.43	0.135
Required Parameters	≤ 500	≤ 5	≤ 10	≤ 5	≤ 10	≤ 140	≥ 0.1	≥ 0.02

^aCalculated using Swiss ADME online server: MW= molecular weight; HBD= hydrogen bond donor; HBA= Hydrogen bond acceptor; rotatable bond= number of rotatable bonds; clog P= partition coefficient log octanol/water; tPSA= total polar surface area

^bCalculated using Molsoft online server: Drug-likeness Score

^cCalculated using BBB predictor: Drug Blood-Brain Barrier permeability (BBB-/BBB+ Score)

Required parameters: all the parameters important for suitable physicochemical properties, drug-like characters, and BBB permeation

Conclusion

Novel sulphonyl pyrimidinone derivatives have been synthesized and show promising therapeutic potential against Alzheimer's disease, as evidenced by a comprehensive set of *in-vitro*, *in-vivo*, and computational studies. In conclusion, the pyrimidinone sulphonyl derivatives produced had good potential as therapeutic agents in the treatment of Alzheimer's disease. The compounds demonstrated successful dual inhibition effect on

acetylcholinesterase and butyrylcholinesterase, which signifies their applicability in the rectification of the cholinergic deficit of the pathology of Alzheimer's. Compounds 4d and 4e that had electron-donating groups were identified as the most promising candidates as they demonstrated better enzyme inhibition and significant cognitive improvement in animal models. The results of the behavior were in line with the in-vitro results, and it was confirmed that these compounds can enhance memory and cognitive performance. Moreover, they were found to be effective using molecular docking studies, which demonstrated the existence of stable interactions at the active sites of both target enzymes, indicating a rational dual-target mechanism of action. Taken together, these results result in sulphonyl pyrimidinone analogs being promising lead compounds in the treatment of Alzheimer's disease. Although the findings are convincing, more mechanistic, pharmacokinetic, and long-term safety research is required to bring these compounds to clinical development as potent multi-target anti-Alzheimer agents.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest relevant to this article.

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Ethical approval

The ethical approval was received from the Institutional Animal Ethics Committee (IAEC) of Shri Rawatpura Sarkar Institute of Pharmacy (Reg. No. SRIP/IAEC/2022-23/B/03), affiliated with CSVTU, Chhattisgarh, and regulated by CPCSEA, New Delhi.

Declaration of consent

Not applicable

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